

Research Symposium: Gaza

Introduction

Nermin Allam, Diana B. Greenwald, and Noora Lori

When we began brainstorming this symposium in December 2023, Israel's military assault on Gaza, in response to the Hamas-led terror attacks of October 7, was entering its third month. At that time, approximately 1,200 Israelis and over 19,000 Palestinians had been killed, with tens of thousands more injured (United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs 2023). Now, as we pen this introduction in late March, 130 hostages remain in captivity, according to the Israeli government, including those who are no longer believed to be alive (Saidel, Said, and Peled 2024). Meanwhile, the death toll for Palestinians in Gaza has surpassed 32,000, according to the Ministry of Health in Gaza (UNOCHA 2024). The World Food Program reports hundreds of thousands are on the brink of famine as Israel continues to obstruct the entry of humanitarian aid into Gaza, plunging some 1.1 million into "catastrophic hunger" and starvation (World Food Programme 2024). At least fifty percent of all buildings in Gaza have been damaged or destroyed in some of the most intensive aerial bombardment and concentrated warfare seen in modern times (Palumbo et al. 2024). Hospitals, schools, mosques, churches, homes, and universities have not been spared bombardment and shelling. As political scientists—not to mention, as mere humans—it is hard not to feel helpless and even, dare we say, hopeless.

Many of us are processing these events amidst a swirling media environment, featuring a regular, graphic stream of civilian suffering and trauma from Gaza, while our feeds

are also peppered with allegations of misinformation and disinformation. Narratives of demonization and dehumanization are feeding into a climate of fear and vulnerability, while we are also witnessing heightened censorship of speech on college campuses and beyond. In sum, this is a fraught time to attempt to apply the tools and lenses of social science. Nonetheless, this is precisely the moment that we should turn to political science—drawing on existing research, methods, and tools for understanding the ferocity and scale of the devastation we are witnessing, its origins, its nature, and its manifold consequences. Further, this is precisely the moment that we should place a mirror in front of political science, considering how the past six months has exposed our discipline's gaps and limitations. Yet, this symposium does not aim to be a self-indulgent exercise in reflection from some distant ivory tower on the epistemological, theoretical, and empirical limitations of the field. Rather, it is an attempt to seriously harness our research efforts to reclaim the humanity of people subjected to daily violence and erasure.

With this in mind, we turned to our colleagues in political science, as well as few scholars from related disciplines (history, anthropology, and international legal studies), to respond to the following question: "What is one prevalent misconception about the conflict, and how can the field of political science effectively respond to this misunderstanding?" Collectively, the pieces highlight the different lenses that political scientists can use to understand the level of violence we are

witnessing, its consequences in the region and beyond, and which policy options are made available or foreclosed based on the language and analytical frames we adopt.

“What is one prevalent misconception about the conflict, and how can the field of political science effectively respond to this misunderstanding?”

bel-Patel and Nahed Samour, and Mark Tessler underscore the importance of moving beyond—or at least supplementing—‘conflict’ frames. Their respective contributions engage with other meaningful conceptual categories such as settler colonialism, apartheid, occupation, siege, and genocide. Dana El Kurd and Amytess Girgis, Neil Ketchley, and Sean Lee explore, in their respective pieces, the understudied connections between what happens in Palestine and broader MENA politics. Still other contributors including Mohammed Abu-Nimer, Yasmeeen Abu Laban, Abigail Bakan, Anwar Mhajne, and Samer Anabtawi describe, and caution against, the politicization and weaponization of identities. Their pieces focus on narratives surrounding religion, anti-Palestinian racism, antisemitism and its relationship to anti-Zionism, the importance of gender-sensitive analysis, and the role of intersectional solidarity from LGBTQ+ communities. Looking forward, the contributors recommend changes in our scholarship. For example, Youssef Chouhoud calls for moving beyond surface-level measures of sympathy for Israelis or Palestinians toward a more nuanced understanding of US public opinion. In our diagnoses for policy making, Jonathan Graubart’s piece, as well as Mark Tessler’s contribution, urge us to avoid repeating the same failed diplomacy of the

Scholars in the symposium covered a wide range of topics. Contributions by Bassam Haddad, Raz Segal, Christine Schwö-

past, and to pay close attention to how the transformation of both Israeli and Palestinian political institutions might empower constituencies for peace. Through this collective space, we present diverse perspectives and voices on the conflict and above all a shared human concern—and agony, over the ongoing human suffering. ♦

References

Palumbo, Daniele, Abdelrahman Abutaleb, Paul Cusiak, and Erwan Rivault. 2024. “At Least Half of Gaza’s Buildings Damaged or Destroyed, New Analysis Shows.” BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-68006607>.

Saidel, Peter, Summer Said, and Anat Peled. 2024. “ Hamas Took More Than 200 Hostages from Israel. Here’s What We Know.” *The Wall Street Journal*. <https://www.wsj.com/world/middle-east/hamas-hostages-israel-gaza-41432124>.

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA). 2023. “Hostilities in the Gaza Strip and Israel | Flash Update #72.” *United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs - occupied Palestinian territory*. <http://www.ochaopt.org/content/hostilities-gaza-strip-and-israel-flash-update-72>.

—. 2024. “Hostilities in the Gaza Strip and Israel | Flash Update #146.” *United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs - occupied Palestinian territory*. <https://www.ochaopt.org/content/hostilities-gaza-strip-and-israel-flash-update-146>.

World Food Programme. 2024. “Famine imminent in northern Gaza, new report warns.” <https://www.wfp.org/news/famine-imminent-northern-gaza-new-report-warns>.